

Development of Flame-retardant Medium Density Wood Fibreboards using Phosphorylated Casein and Polyamidoamine-epichlorohydrin Resin

Hanbin Lee, Nam Kyeun Kim and Debes Bhattacharyya

Centre for Advanced Materials Manufacturing and Design, The Department of Mechanical and Mechatronics Engineering, The University of Auckland, New Zealand

ICCM-24 Baltimore, Aug 4 – Aug 8, 2025

CENTRE FOR ADVANCED MATERIALS
MANUFACTURING & DESIGN

UNIVERSITY OF
AUCKLAND
Waipapa Taumata Rau
NEW ZEALAND

Background

Medium Density Fibreboard

- A type of engineering wood product
- Consisting of wood fibre and binder
- Good quality of surface

Application

- Furniture
- kitchen cabinets
- Mouldings
- door parts
- laminate flooring

1

Getting wood chips from pulp, waste, residual wood and logging

2

Removing impurities from chips after screening

3

Refining wood chips using pressurised refiners (pressurised disk refining)

4

Blending wood fibres with binders and sometimes wax

5

Forming a mat and hot pressing

6

Cooling and cutting to size

Fire Resistant Study

-
- (In 1963) Inorganic chemicals in solid pine wood, analysed by residual char weight measurement; Browne & Tang
 - (In 1983) Polyurethan-based FR coating on plywood surfaces in the ASTM E119-20; White et al
 - (In 2012) Nanoclay in UF-based MDF, analysed by TGA; Reza et al
 - (In 2019) Combination of different types of chemicals in MUF-based MDF, analysed by cone calorimeter; George et al

Binder Toxicology Study

-
- (In 1992) Suspected formaldehyde emission from pressed-wood products; Oston & Fellin
 - (In 1998) Regulated formaldehyde emission from building materials; Kavvouras et al
 - (In 2004) Categorized formaldehyde as carcinogenic for humans; Gatlin et al
 - (In 2013) MUF culminating the desirable bonding strength of MDF, but still higher emission of the formaldehyde; Zhang et al
 - (In 2018) Combination of UF and MF complying with formaldehyde emission regulations (EC-32-17); Zhang et al

Fire hazard

- (In 2007) The addition of 6 % inorganic salts, such as borax and diammonium phosphate, decreased the internal bond strength by ~33 % in the PF-based MDF samples; Ayrilmis et al
- (In 2009) The incorporation of 30 % mineral-based chemicals, such as sodium aluminate and aluminium trihydrate, dropped the internal bond strength of the UF-based MDF samples by ~26 %; Hashim et al

- Corrosive side effect
- Toxic fumes (during combustion)
- Mechanical properties drops

Toxic binder

- (In 2000) Adverse health effects (nausea, eye, and throat irritation) in humans at more than 0.1 mg/L airborne formaldehyde concentration ; Athanassiadou
- MDF products made in NZ based on a MUF binder have 0.3 mg/L formaldehyde emission that complies with JIA A 5905 standard (Max. 0.5 mg/L of formaldehyde emission)

- Residual formaldehyde in the binder
- Process of the binder manufacture
- Hydrolytic degradation of the cured binder, particularly under high temperature and humidity

Motivation and Concept

• Combination binder system

Polyamidoamine-epichlorohydrin (PAE)

- ✓ Relatively low toxicity
- ✓ Good bonding with natural materials

Casein

- ✓ Char forming ability due to a rich of acid sources and blowing agents (carboxyl/sialic groups & amine groups)
- ✓ The excellent flame-retardant performance of casein has been identified in different material systems (textile substrates and polymer composites); Alongi et al and Zhang et al

- Material composition of MDF panels

Sample	PAE (%)	Casein (%)	Moisture content (%)
4.4PAE8	4.4	-	8
4.4PAE8 30CP	4.4	30	8

- Manufacturing parameters

Resin content (%)	Moisture content (%)	Hot-pressing time (s)	Hot-pressing temperature (°C)	Target density (kg/m ³)
4.4	8	150	180	750

- ✓ Moisture content (MC) and the resin ratio were suggested from the supplier.
- ✓ Parameters are from the previous research regarding formaldehyde-free resin-based MDF manufacture.
- ✓ The resin system is a combination of modified soy flour and PAE resin.
- ✓ A density range of MDF is 650 – 800 kg/m³

Manufacture of Casein-based MDF

- Effect of casein on heat release rate of MDF

Heat release rate (HRR)

- ✓ The rate of fire growth
- ✓ The size of the fire
- ✓ An effective heat of combustion

The addition of 30 % casein particles reduces the peak heat release rate of the MDF sample by ~ 7 %.

Mechanical Properties

- Mechanical properties of PAE-based MDF samples using casein particles

➤ Flexural strength

➤ Internal bond (IB) strength

Phosphorylation of Casein

- 1** Preparing 0.01 M sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution to make a pH 12 environment. Heating the NaOH solution at 40 °C.
- 2** Casein particles are added when the solution temperature reaches 40 °C. Sodium trimetaphosphate (STMP) is slowly added. (when STMP is added, the pH value decreases due to the reaction)
- 3** Dropping 1 M hydrogen chloride (HCl) or NaOH in the casein-STMP solution to remain the pH value at 12. Total reaction time is 1 hour.
- 4** Quenching the reaction by the removal of the heat. Decreasing the pH value at 4 by dropwise addition of 1 M HCl.
- 5** Collecting the treated casein curd by a coffee sieve and washing them with distilled water.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

- 752 cm^{-1} is the most important peak to identify the bonding formation of hydroxide groups (casein) and phosphate groups (STMP) through phosphorylation.
- Other vibration bands; 522, 987, 1100, and 1282 cm^{-1} are attributed to O-P-O, P-OH, P-OH, and P=O stretching, respectively.

Energy dispersive X-ray (EDX)

- Elemental composition of casein and phosphorylated casein

- ✓ Sodium (Na) and choline (Cl) contents in the structure of the phosphorylated casein increase by 2.3 % and 1.6 %, respectively.

Heat release rate (HRR)

- ✓ The rate of fire growth
- ✓ The size of the fire
- ✓ An effective heat of combustion

✓ **The addition of 30 % phosphorylated casein particles most effectively reduces the peak heat release rate of the MDF sample by ~ 25 %.**

Mechanical Properties

- **Effects of 30 % P-CP addition on mechanical properties of 4.4PAE8 MDF**

- **Flexural strength**

- **Internal bond (IB) strength**

Hypothetical Reaction Disturbance

Polyamidoamine-epichlorohydrin (PAE)

- ✓ It is assumed that sodium carboxylate ($-\text{COONa}$) like a sodium salt may not function as a carboxyl group capable of reacting with the azetidinium group of the PAE.

- Casein was successfully phosphorylated to improve its char forming capability.
- **MDF panels with density of $\sim 730 \text{ kg/m}^3$ were manufactured using casein powder and PAE resin as a formaldehyde-free binder.**
- Phosphorylated casein reduced peak heat release rate ($\sim 25\%$) of MDF with more effective char formation in comparison with one of the panel with non-treated casein.
- **The addition of phosphorylated casein to the MDF improved both flexural modulus (23 %) and stress (16 %), compared to the panel with non-treated casein.**
- Phosphorylation of casein retained internal bond strength of MDF.